

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

D3.5 - Access representation ontology developed for project's cohorts

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1. Executive Summary

Access, reuse and integration of biomedical datasets is critical to advance genomics research and realise benefits to human health. However, obtaining human controlled-access data in a timely fashion can be challenging, as neither the access requests nor the data uses conditions are standardised: their manual review and evaluation by a Data Access Committee (DAC) to determine whether access should be granted or not can significantly delay the process, typically by at least 4 to 6 weeks once the dataset of interest has been identified.

To address this, we have contributed to the development of the Data Use Ontology (DUO), which was approved as a Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) standard and has been used in over 200,000 annotations worldwide. DUO has already been implemented in some CINECA cohort and cohort data sharing resources (e.g. EGA, H3Africa, synthetic datasets); additional cohorts are in the process of reviewing data access policies with a view of applying DUO terms to their datasets. DUO is natively supported by Beacon V2, used by WP1 for discovery queries. Users can query through WP1 infrastructure for datasets consistent with the DUO terms representing their research purposes or additional restrictions, increasing findability of suitable datasets as well as preventing potentially unnecessary data access requests for unsuitable ones. As WP2 embeds DUO into the Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure they are developing, we anticipate the data access process for CINECA cohorts to become more streamlined and consequently shorter, improving data access and reuse.

2. Project objectives

WP3 Task 3.5 objectives:

1. Review and integrate current community efforts for data access representation into an ontology
2. Build the ontology using semantic standards, and deploy iterative versions on the Ontology Lookup Service
3. Deploy and evaluate the ontology in CINECA

3. Background, content and implementation of DUO

The development process of DUO has been extensively described in (1). Several community efforts have been reviewed and included in the development of the DUO content. DUO is a machine readable structured vocabulary, formally expressed using the World Wide Web Consortium web ontology language (OWL) standard. Its development follows best practices in the biomedical ontology domain, and it has been registered with the OBO Foundry. (2) As of November 2021 DUO contains 25 terms representing two types of data use terms, permissions and modifiers, as shown on Figure 1:

- Permission terms include “general research use,” “health or medical or biomedical use,” “disease specific research,” and “population origins or ancestry research only” and are expressly permitted uses or focused areas of research.
- Modifier terms add requirements, limitations, or prohibitions within the permitted boundary.

Figure 1. The current DUO contains Permission and Modifier terms. (adapted from (1)) DUO contains 25 terms representing two types of data use terms, permissions and modifiers. Permissions standardize allowed usage of the datasets. Modifiers are used to further qualify main categories of controlled access.

DUO has been implemented to annotate genomics datasets worldwide. As of November 2021, implementers include repositories, databases, and projects in North America, Europe, Africa, Asia, and Australia, as shown on Figure 2.

Figure 2. Current implementations of the Data Use Ontology. As of November 2021, implementers include repositories, databases, and projects in North America, Europe, Africa, Asia, and Australia. From (1)

3.2 DUO workflows in CINECA

3.2.1 Implementation in the European Genome-Phenome Archive

Figure 3 shows the typical data workflow at the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA).

Figure 3. EGA facilitates the submission, discovery, access, and distribution of sensitive human data. A researcher submits controlled access human genetic, phenotypic and clinical data to EGA after

signing a Data Processing Agreement (1). EGA processes, archives, and releases the dataset to be findable. Another researcher discovers data of interest at the EGA (2). They contact the Data Access Committee for the data of interest and agree to the terms of data reuse by signing a Data Access Agreement (3). The Data Access Committee informs EGA that access is approved (4). The EGA grants access to the requesting researcher (5) who can then download and visualise the data (6). GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation. Figure reproduced from (3)

1. Addition of DUO term(s) to EGA datasets

DUO can be added to datasets at the EGA by two routes.

The most commonly used method is for the submitter to choose appropriate DUO term(s) for their dataset(s) using the most up to date version of the ontology, always available from <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/duo.owl>. Once they have identified the most appropriate DUO term(s) for their dataset(s) they provide them to the EGA by emailing helpdesk on helpdesk@ega-archive.org. The helpdesk team then runs an in-house script that assigns the DUO term(s) to the dataset(s) which in turn propagates through to the EGA website.

Submitters can also add DUO terms themselves if they are submitting [programmatically](#) to the EGA. In this method, the “data_use” attribute (submitted to EGA in XML format) is used to store the desired DUO term(s) along with the version which references the ontology used from a given build.

e.g,

```
<DATA_USES>
  <DATA_USE ontology="DUO" code="0000042" version="23-02-2021"/>
</DATA_USES>
```

In some instances DUO can be used in combination with a modifier¹ to allow more detailed description of how the data may be used. For example, DUO:0000007 (disease specific research) should be used in combination with terms from MONDO to describe specifically which disease research the data can be used for e.g., DUO:0000007 MONDO:0000996 would mean that the data could only be used for research into prostate lymphoma. While DUO terms can be used with terms from any disease ontology, using MONDO terms is recommended to prevent further mappings between different disease ontologies for example. In order to submit this programmatically the user would use a modifier attribute within the XML e.g.,

```
<DATA_USE ontology="DUO" code="0000007" version="23-02-2021">
  <MODIFIER>
    <DB>MONDO</DB>
    <ID>0000996</ID>
  </MODIFIER>
```

¹ Note that EGA modifiers are modifiers on DUO terms (DUO permissions and DUO modifiers).

2. Rendering of DUO term(s) on the EGA website

On the EGA website, users can search using DUO terms and retrieve datasets of interest. For example, Figure 4 shows a dataset consented for disease specific research (DUO:0000007) where the disease is further specified by using the MONDO term MONDO:0004992 - cancer.

The screenshot shows the EGA website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and a navigation menu with options: ABOUT, SUBMISSION, BROWSE, ACCESS, DOWNLOAD, METADATA, Helpdesk, and Log in. The main content area displays the dataset ID A108870A. Below this, there is a table with columns: Dataset ID, Technology, and Samples. The table contains one row: EGAD00001007598, HiSeq X Five, 5. Underneath, there is a 'Dataset Description' section with the text: 'Whole genome sequencing for single cells for library A108870A 1795 cells; filetype=bam'. A 'Data Use Conditions' section follows, with a row of buttons: DS, PUB, IRB, UE, PS, IS. Below this is a link to 'Data Use Conditions'. A table of conditions is shown with columns: Label, Code, Version, and Modifier. The table contains six rows of conditions. Finally, there is a section titled 'Who controls access to this dataset' with a contact person: Sarah Jane Lee, Email: tsadmin[at]phsa[dot]ca, and More details: EGAC00001001636.

Dataset ID	Technology	Samples
EGAD00001007598	HiSeq X Five	5

Label	Code	Version	Modifier
disease specific research	DUO:0000007	2019-01-07	MONDO:0004992
publication required	DUO:0000019	2019-01-07	
ethics approval required	DUO:0000021	2019-01-07	
user specific restriction	DUO:0000026	2019-01-07	
project specific restriction	DUO:0000027	2019-01-07	
institution specific restriction	DUO:0000028	2019-01-07	

Figure 4. Screenshot from the EGA website, <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001007598>. Datasets in EGA can be annotated with DUO terms, making them searchable based on access conditions. Here, a dataset with a disease research specific condition is associated with the MONDO term MONDO:0004992, which denotes cancer in the MONDO ontology.

3.2.2 Implementation in H3Africa

H3Africa datasets (20 individual datasets of genotype and/or phenotype data from participants recruited by different H3Africa projects. The projects focus on different disease areas) are submitted to the EGA under controlled access. Prior to submission, the H3ABioNet ontologies team works with H3Africa PIs to map their consent information to DUO terms. The DUO mappings are sent to EGA and made available on the EGA website. The mappings are also available in the H3Africa Data and

Biospecimen catalogue (<https://catalog.h3africa.org/>) (Figure 5), which provide an interface to search for H3Africa datasets in EGA and biospecimens in the biorepositories. Users can select results of interest and submit an online request to the access committee. The DUO codes linked to datasets provide information to requesters on any restrictions on data use prior to submission of their request. They also enable the access committee to check that the request for data use is in line with the participant's consents.

In the case where tiered consent may be available, information on the consent level that each participant in a dataset selected is not usually available electronically, making it difficult to generalize DUO codes across a study. To address this, in a separate project at UCT, under the CIDRI Africa Wellcome Trust Centre, an electronic consent form has been developed as a REDCap module. The form makes use of DUO descriptions, thus making it easier to add DUO codes electronically at the individual level rather than at a study level.

Title	Acronym	Design	EGA Accession	Data use codes	Participants	Biospecimens	Paired
The Genomics of Schizophrenia in the South African Xhosa People	SAX		Unavailable	Unavailable	0	2238	0
Genetic determinants of susceptibility to trypanosomiasis	TrypanoGEN	Case	EGAS00001002602	DUO:0000006 DUO:0000027 DUO:0000024 DUO:0000019 DUO:0000021	233	0	0
H3Africa Chip Design Study	H3AChip	Control	EGAS00001002976	DUO:0000006 DUO:0000027 DUO:0000024 DUO:0000019 DUO:0000021	348	379	104
Stroke Investigative Research & Educational Network	SIREN		Unavailable	Unavailable	0	6001	0
Collaborative African Genomics Network	CAFGEN	Case-Control	EGAS00001002656	DUO:0000006 DUO:0000027 DUO:0000024 DUO:0000019 DUO:0000021	314	1804	306
Genomic and Environmental Risk Factors for Cardiometabolic Disease in Africans	AWI-Gen	Case-Control	EGAS00001002482	DUO:0000006 DUO:0000027 DUO:0000024 DUO:0000019 DUO:0000014 DUO:0000015	971	13415	0

Figure 5. H3Africa Data and Biospecimen catalogue webinterface listing the studies available and the DUO mappings based on the study consent forms.

3.2.3 Implementation in BBMRI-ERIC

BBMRI-ERIC Directory²(4) is a findability service developed and operated by BBMRI-ERIC in order to allow researchers and other users of the research infrastructure, to identify biobanks and biomolecular resources which might have data and biological material available for their research projects. The Directory is describing *biobanks* as organisational units, hosting *collections* of data and biological material.

BBMRI-ERIC is aiming to streamline the access process when the requesters are only requesting access to the data. While the full complexity of this is still being solved, the Directory has recently adopted DUO in order to describe reuse restrictions specifically for the data available in the collections. Zero or more DUO terms can be provided as attributes on the collection level. These are combined with the existing attributes and allow the biobank/collection representatives to specify those terms that are common for all the data in the given collection as shown on Figure 6. Biobanks can use subcollections to precisely describe data that is governed by the same data access conditions. We are considering implementing a search facet to allow a researcher to filter the Directory based on the DUO terms.

[< Back](#)

Collection

COVID Vaccine - IRCCS Ospedale Sacro Cuore Don Calabria

[Add to selection](#)

Description: The collection includes different specimens collected at different time points from a cohort of 2000 health care workers of IRCCS Sacro Cuore Don Calabria Hospital and subjected to vaccination for SARS-CoV-2 using the mRNA BNT162b2 (Pfizer) vaccine. The cohort includes naïve and subjects with history of previous SARS-CoV-2 infection, documented by molecular testing.. Specimens collected and stored at -80 °C: serum for all 2000 subjects, blood (for about 300 subjects in DMSO) and plasma (for 80 ... [show more](#) v

Id: bbmri-eric:ID:IT_1605519998080235:collection:6b6a977b0b9d4f7
Size: 13060 samples
Age: 18-70 Year
Type: Prospective study
Sex: Male Female
Materials: Serum Plasma Whole Blood
Storage: -60°C to -80°C
Data: Antibodies titer (IgM and IgG) Data on clinical symptoms Survey data Other
Data use conditions: project specific restriction health or medical or biomedical research disease specific research ethics approval required biomedical research method development

Contact Information

Head/PI: PIUBELLI CHIARA (Biologo)

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[Email](#)
[+390456014871](#)

Biobank

TROPICA BIOBANK - IRCCS Ospedale Sacro Cuore Don Calabria
 IRCCS Ospedale Sacro Cuore Don Calabria
 Italy

[View TROPICA BIOBANK - IRCCS Ospedale Sacro Cuore Don Calabria](#)

[Website](#)
[Email](#)

Partner charter: no

Biobank id: bbmri-eric:ID:IT_1605519998080235

Networks

Name: BBMRI.it Network
[View BBMRI.it Network network](#)

Name: COVID_19
[View COVID_19 network](#)

Collaboration

Commercial: yes
Not for profit: yes

² <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/>

Figure 6. Screenshot from the BBMRI-ERIC website showing use of DUO terms on a COVID Vaccine related collection. From

https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:IT_1605519998080235:collection:6b6a977b0b9d4f7

3.3 DUO powered applications

3.3.1 DUO-powered discovery in CINECA

CINECA uses version two of the GA4GH Beacon standard for data and dataset discovery, and has been a part of shaping that standard and its implementations to support its data needs. As part of that work, DUO has been incorporated into the dataset definition for the Beacon standard³; specifically, it is part of the Beacon v2 model⁴. All replies from CINECA beacons will report the DUO consent codes when supplied, and part of cohort onboarding will include helping cohorts provide that information. While DUO codes are present in the Beacon specification, one objective for next year is to facilitate their implementation when deploying Beacons. Development of Beacon portals continues, and that development work will include searching for data that matches required DUO codes. A prototype of a CINECA portal is available at <https://service-registry-demo.ega-archive.org/cohorts>.

3.3.2 Data Use Oversight System (DUOS) for automated data access workflow

In (5), Cabili et al. describe implementation of a DUO-powered system to automate access request evaluation against data use conditions present on datasets, where both are encoded using DUO. They find that they were able to structure 118/123 of the evaluated Data Use Limitations (96%) and 52/52 (100%) of research proposals using DUO terminology, and that DUOS' automated data access adjudication in all cases agreed with the DAC manual review. This is a first step in validating the suitability of DUO to automate data access as shown on Figure 7. To enable full automation, DUO recommend standards for modifiers to be used and which are expected to be natively supported by DUO-powered tools. For users who can't or prefer to not use those standard there is no guarantee that a decision can be made automatically, though we can imagine some tools may be able to rely on online mapping services such as Oxo, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/oxo/>.

³ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/specification-v2/issues/51>

⁴ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2-Models#readme>

Figure 7. DUO-based automated workflow for data access, from (5)

3.3.3 Resource Entitlement Management System (REMS) for automated data access workflow

The Finnish ELIXIR node has implemented an open source tool “REMS⁵” to help Data Access Committees (DAC) to manage the data access process. An authenticated researcher can submit an electronic Data Access Request (DAR) pertaining to an identified dataset. REMS circulates the DAR to the competent DAC for a review. For approved DARs, REMS issues GA4GH Passport visas (6) describing the researcher’s permission to access the dataset in the computing environment.

A publicly available demo instance at <https://rems-demo.rahtiapp.fi>. Figure 8 shows how the GA4GH Passport standard for authentication is implemented in REMS for example. Use of DUO by data users and stewards could streamline approval processes for datasets.

⁵ <https://github.com/CSCfi/rems/>

Figure 8. Implementation of GA4GH Passport such as in REMS. From (6)

In WP2, ELIXIR Finland, hosted by CSC - the IT Center for Science Ltd, is developing DUO support to REMS to help the DAC to match datasets' DUO terms with the properties of the applicant's project. In the DAR, the researcher describes their research project using DUO codes. Provided the datasets have DUO tagging in place and imported to REMS, the tool matches the DAR's DUO codes against those of the datasets and generates to the DAC a proposal to approve or reject the DAR. The approach is similar to (5).

Further integration of DUO terms within Passport visas would open the way to sharing researcher profiles and permissions across DACs. This could enable users to automatically gain access to existing and new datasets complying with the level of permissions they have already been granted by a known, trusted DAC.

3.4 Next Steps

CINECA will be a driving project to help GA4GH integrate DUO terms into Passport visas as shown above. In addition to technical developments needed to support this, we will engage with different governance and oversight bodies such as IRBs (Institutional Review Boards) and/or DACs to advocate for policy shift in approving access to groups of datasets by data use profile rather than individualized datasets. For example, this was done through engaging with the Harvard Catalyst group⁶, which encompasses several Boston area's IRBs. This will allow authenticated researchers to automatically access new and existing datasets matching their DAC-approved data use profile after sign-in. Longer term we envision that it will be possible to create authenticated users

⁶ <https://catalyst.harvard.edu/>

through Passport, associated with a profile describing the authorized level of usage, that could be shared across DACs that have established reciprocal trust relationships.

While DUO has reached a stable level of development as showcased by global implementation, we know that it will need to evolve to cover additional use cases from new partners, such as adding terms to enable integration of multiple datasets for example. Ongoing development will be guided by the DUO governance policy⁷ to ensure fitness for purpose and consider only requests supported by strong use cases.

4. References

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5. Empirical validation of an automated approach to data use oversight. *Cell Genomics.* 2021 Nov 10;1(2):100031.
6. GA4GH Passport standard for digital identity and access permissions. *Cell Genomics.* 2021 Nov 10;1(2):100030.

5. Abbreviations

DAC	Data Access Committee
DAR	Data Access Request
DUO	Data Use Ontology
DUOS	Data Use Oversight System
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
GA4GH	The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

⁷ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO/blob/master/Governance2021.md>

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H3Africa	Human, Heredity and Health in Africa
IRB	Institutional Review Board
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology
OWL	Web Ontology Language
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
UCT	University of Cape Town
WP	Work Package

6. Work Packages in CINECA

- WP1 - Federated Data Discovery and Querying
- WP2 - Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
- WP3 - Cohort Level Meta Data Representation
- WP4 - Federated Joint Cohort Analysis
- WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications
- WP6 - Outreach, training and dissemination
- WP7 - Ethical and legal governance framework for transnational data-sharing
- WP8 - Project Management and coordination
- WP9 - Ethics requirements

7. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is on time.

8. Appendices

id	shorthand	label	definition
DUO:0000021	IRB	ethics approval required	This data use modifier indicates that the requestor must provide documentation of local IRB/ERB approval.
DUO:0000006	HMB	health or medical or biomedical research	This data use permission indicates that use is allowed for health/medical/biomedical purposes; does not include the study of population origins or ancestry.

DUO:0000019	PUB	publication required	This data use modifier indicates that requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community.
DUO:0000026	US	user specific restriction	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to use by approved users.
DUO:0000044	NPOA	population origins or ancestry research prohibited	This data use modifier indicates use for purposes of population origin or ancestry research is prohibited.
DUO:0000020	COL	collaboration required	This data use modifier indicates that the requestor must agree to collaboration with the primary study investigator(s).
DUO:0000046	NCU	non-commercial use only	This data use modifier indicates that use of the data is limited to not-for-profit use.
DUO:0000018	NPUNCU	not for profit, non commercial use only	This data use modifier indicates that use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations and not-for-profit use, non-commercial use.
DUO:0000012	RS	research specific restrictions	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to studies of a certain research type.
DUO:0000025	TS	time limit on use	This data use modifier indicates that use is approved for a specific number of months.
DUO:0000004	NRES	no restriction	This data use permission indicates there is no restriction on use.
DUO:0000045	NPU	not for profit organisation use only	This data use modifier indicates that use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations.

DUO:0000017		data use modifier	Data use modifiers indicate additional conditions for use.
DUO:0000011	POA	population origins or ancestry research only	This data use permission indicates that use of the data is limited to the study of population origins or ancestry.
DUO:0000024	MOR	publication moratorium	This data use modifier indicates that the requester agrees not to publish results of studies until a specific date.
DUO:0000016	GSO	genetic studies only	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to genetic studies only (i.e., studies that include genotype research alone or both genotype and phenotype research, but not phenotype research exclusively)
DUO:0000029	RTN	return to database or resource	This data use modifier indicates that the requestor must return derived/enriched data to the database/resource.
DUO:0000043	CC	clinical care use	This data use modifier indicates that use is allowed for clinical use and care.
DUO:0000015	NMDS	no general methods research	This data use modifier indicates that use does not allow methods development research (e.g., development of software or algorithms).
DUO:0000028	IS	institution specific restriction	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to use within an approved institution.
DUO:0000022	GS	geographical restriction	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to within a specific geographic region.

DUO:0000007	DS	disease specific research	This data use permission indicates that use is allowed provided it is related to the specified disease.
DUO:0000001		data use permission	A data item that is used to indicate consent permissions for datasets and/or materials, and relates to the purposes for which datasets and/or material might be removed, stored or used.
DUO:0000042	GRU	general research use	This data use permission indicates that use is allowed for general research use for any research purpose.
DUO:0000027	PS	project specific restriction	This data use modifier indicates that use is limited to use within an approved project.

Table A1. DUO terms as of February 23rd 2021. Each term has a stable identifier (column 1, "ID"), an optional shorthand (column 2) that can be used for visualisation purposes as shown on Figure 4, a label (column 3) and a textual definition (column 4). Empty cells indicate there is no content for those values.

